

A FAST.Farm and MATLAB/Simulink interface for wind farm control design

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Abstract. Increasing the efficiency of wind farms is important for speeding up the transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources. Current wind farm control relies on maximization of power generation of individual turbines. However, research has demonstrated that plant-wide wind farm control could optimize the performance of a wind farm. Wind farm simulation tools are crucial in designing, testing, and validating wind farm controls. FAST.Farm is a recently developed multi-physics engineering tool for modeling wind farm performance by solving the aero-hydro-servoelastic dynamics of each individual turbine. The capabilities of FAST.Farm for control design purposes can be extended through a co-simulation with MATLAB/Simulink. Therefore a MATLAB/Simulink interface with FAST.Farm has been developed. The construction and working of this interface are explained in this paper. This interface supports developing and testing advanced closed-loop control at the wind turbine and wind farm levels.

1. Introduction

There is a consensus in the scientific community that we need to transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources quickly in order to attenuate the rise of the average temperature on earth [1, 2]. Large onshore and offshore wind farms are being built to increase the share of renewable energy in the current power systems. The share of wind energy in the total energy production in Europe was around 16% in 2020, with the expectation that this will rise to 25% in 2025 [3, 4]. To reach the ambitious goal of decarbonization, for example, the Dutch government recently assigned additional zones in the North Sea for offshore wind farm development [5].

The development of wind farm controllers progresses as well, as the number and size of wind farms increase, but is still at the research stage. Current practice defers control to the turbine level, where individual wind turbine controllers rely on the concept of greedy control. In greedy control, each wind turbine in a wind farm optimizes its own power production, without sharing information about the aerodynamic coupling with other turbines in the farm. However, research has demonstrated that applying these greedy controllers across the farm is sub-optimal in terms of overall plant performance [6, 7]. Current research on wind farm control aims to develop controllers which take into account the wake interactions within a wind farm and the performance of individual turbines [8, 9]. These controllers aim to minimize the costs of wind energy by considering, among others, structural degradation and grid integration objectives. For

designing these controllers it is important that the relevant physics of a wind farm are accurately modeled so that the estimated turbine performance corresponds to reality.

There already exist several engineering tools for modeling the physics of a wind farm. These tools are used for wind farm control synthesis and validation. A distinction can be made between low-, medium- and high-fidelity tools. Low-fidelity models, e.g. FLORIS [10], are based on parametric flow models. These models estimate only quasi-steady wake characteristics for wind farm layout optimization and cannot predict dynamic flow development. On the other hand, high-fidelity tools like SOWFA [11] estimate the flow field in detail by resolving the governing equations (Navier-Stokes) in three-dimensional (3-D) space. However, high-fidelity tools are impractical in use because of the high computation time. FAST.Farm is a recently developed medium-fidelity multiphysics engineering tool by National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) which aims to balance the need for accurate modeling of the relevant physics while maintaining low computational cost. This tool uses a simplified (two-dimensional) version of the governing equations in which the Navier-Stokes (NS) equations are approximated with a thin shear layer approximation that is less computationally expensive than high-fidelity tools [12, 13]. Therefore, FAST.Farm shows to be a promising tool for designing wind farm controllers and simulating wind farm behavior [14].

The current procedure of wind farm control synthesis in FAST.Farm is by constructing wind farm controllers in Fortran language. These wind farm controllers are called Super Controllers (SC), which are often compiled in Dynamic Link Libraries (DLL). The SC-DLL is essentially identical to the SC available in SOWFA [15]. An SC-DLL is used in conjunction with individual wind turbine controllers designed in the style of the DISCON DLL [16]. A drawback of constructing a wind farm controller in a Fortran DLL is that Fortran is a compiled language made for performance and lacks flexibility and interactivity compared with MATLAB/Simulink. MATLAB/Simulink is a widespread tool in the control community which has well-established toolboxes for designing high-level controllers. A MATLAB/Simulink interface with FAST.Farm would allow the wind community to easily implement wind farm control algorithms from the MATLAB platform, as well as extend those controllers with pre-built features.

The contribution of this paper is to present the first, to the best of the authors' knowledge, interface between FAST.Farm and MATLAB/Simulink, including its construction and how to operate it. Such an interface extends the capability of FAST.Farm for control design purposes. This interface is realized by linking the individual turbine controllers in the FAST.Farm tool to MATLAB through a Message Passing Interface (MPI) and MATLAB EXecutable (MEX) functions. This interface supports a co-simulation between FAST.Farm and MATLAB/Simulink, making it able to run the controllers, at both turbine and wind farm levels, and simulation simultaneously.

The structure of this paper is as follows. First, the setup of the FAST.Farm and MATLAB/Simulink interface is detailed in section 2. Next, section 3 describes the outcome of a case study that shows the working of the interface. Finally, section 4 concludes the paper.

2. MATLAB/Simulink and FAST.Farm interface

MATLAB and Simulink are both developed by Mathworks, which is specialized in developing mathematical computing software [17]. MATLAB is primarily used for analyzing and visualizing data, as well as developing algorithms, while Simulink is a graphical simulation environment used for designing dynamical systems. Simulink can be used as an add-on to MATLAB. The MATLAB/Simulink and FAST.Farm interface is realized by linking the individual turbine controllers in the FAST.Farm tool to MATLAB through a MPI and MEX functions. On the side of FAST.Farm, an MPI is connected to the individual turbine controllers of each OpenFAST instance. There exists one OpenFAST instance for each wind turbine simulated in FAST.Farm. An MPI is used to exchange messages between multiple computers or programs running a parallel

program across distributed memory. This MPI connection facilitates the exchange of messages between the turbine controllers in FAST.Farm and other programs. On the MATLAB side, MEX functions are used to enable communication with external programs, by linking to a C/C++ or Fortran shared library. In this way, MATLAB calls the MPI interface through the use of MEX functions, and therefore messages are exchanged between the turbine controllers and MATLAB. Figure 1 depicts the calling sequence of the interface of a wind farm in FAST.Farm with three wind turbines. The message that is sent back and forth between FAST.Farm and MATLAB is stacked in the so-called `avrSWAP` matrix [18]. This matrix contains all the measurement information and control parameters of each wind turbine in vectors. Having access to this structure information, MATLAB can read and modify the matrix accordingly and subsequently send back the matrix with the updated control parameters to FAST.Farm. The remaining of this section is as follows. Section 2.1 explains the construction of the MPI interface. The setup of the MEX functions in MATLAB is outlined in section 2.2. Last, section 2.3 explains the expansion to Simulink.

Figure 1: Calling sequence between FAST.Farm and MATLAB/Simulink.

2.1. MPI interface in FAST.Farm

FAST.Farm can exchange messages with other programs through an MPI interface. Herein, the so-called message is the `avrSWAP` matrix. Initially, the DLLs of the turbine controllers in each OpenFAST instance receive controller commands from the SC in FAST.Farm. The SC-DLL of FAST.Farm is essentially identical to the super controller available in SOWFA [15]. The SC-DLL is used in conjunction with individual wind turbine controllers designed in the style of the DISCON DLL (originally used in Bladed) [16]. Instead of using an SC-DLL, the DLLs of the internal turbine controller are modified in order to link them to an MPI. Then, FAST.Farm can exchange measurement data and controller commands with MATLAB/Simulink through the MPI. The interface is designed in a scalable way preserving the parallelized structure of FAST.farm. The MPI interface supports the calling sequence of FAST.Farm in which FAST.Farm only accepts updated messages after completing the previous time-step. The MPI interface supports both the implementation of wind turbine and wind farm controllers. In general, a wind farm controller determines reference yaw angles and power set-points for all the wind turbines in a wind farm. Consequently, wind turbine controllers compute the associated generator torque and blade-pitch angles. When it comes to turbine-level controls, one can choose whether to still use a standard Bladed-Style DLL like DTUWEC [19] or ROSCO [20], or get them from MATLAB/Simulink. In the latter, which is the case in this paper, the MPI directly links MATLAB/Simulink to OpenFAST.

2.2. MATLAB Interface with MEX Functions

On the side of MATLAB, four MEX functions are written to establish a connection between MATLAB and the MPI. Hence, information can be exchanged between MATLAB and the

OpenFAST instances. The four MEX functions are named *Initialise*, *Receive*, *Send*, and *Stop*. Figure 2 depicts the calling sequence of the MEX functions in the MATLAB/Simulink environment.

Figure 2: Calling sequence of MEX functions in MATLAB/Simulink.

- **Initialise:** This function is needed to initiate the connection between the MPI server and MATLAB. The purpose of this function is to connect the right internal ports in order to exchange messages between the MPI server and MATLAB.
- **Receive:** By calling this function the `avrSWAP` matrix is retrieved from FAST.Farm to MATLAB/Simulink. The `avrSWAP` matrix is only updated for one (random) turbine. This function ensures that FAST.Farm has performed a new simulation time-step before it retrieves the matrix.
- **Send:** By calling this function the updated `avrSWAP` matrix is sent back to FAST.Farm. FAST.Farm waits for the updated matrix before it performs a new simulation time-step for the same turbine.
- **Stop:** The stop function terminates the connection between the MPI server and MATLAB once the total run time has been reached. This function is needed to prevent memory leakage.

The structure in MATLAB contains a farm-level loop and a turbine-level loop, see Algorithm 1. This algorithm offers the possibility to separately include a turbine-level controller and a farm-level controller at the indicated lines and preserves the parallel computing features of FAST.Farm. In general, wind farm controllers have a lower sampling rate than wind turbine controllers. Within a farm-level time-step, turbine signals are updated and released in parallel independent from each other. At the wind turbine level, FAST.Farm and MATLAB/Simulink perform a co-simulation in which both programs simultaneously update measurements or control variables for different turbines in any order. Once all turbines have reached the next farm-level time-step, the farm-level loop proceeds. After the total run time, the algorithm terminates the connection.

Algorithm 1 FAST.Farm and MATLAB interface

```

Initialise
while true do
  incomplete = true
  % Update farm-level control here
  while incomplete do
    Receive
    % Update turbine-level control here
    Send
  end while
end while
Stop
  
```

2.3. Simulink interface

Simulink offers the possibility to visualize controllers in a graphical block diagram. This makes Simulink a more intuitive tool for designing controllers than MATLAB. Messages that are received in MATLAB can be redirected to Simulink with the use of System Functions (S-Functions). S-Functions are MATLAB scripts that can be run in Simulink within a level 2 S-Function block. Two level 2 S-Function blocks, Receive and Send, are constructed in Simulink in order to exchange the `avrSWAP` matrix between MATLAB and Simulink. See Figure 3 for the visualization in Simulink.

Figure 3: Block diagram in Simulink of FAST.Farm and Simulink interface.

3. Case Study

Two test cases have been set up to show the working of the MATLAB/Simulink and FAST.Farm interface. These test cases verify the implementation of the MATLAB/Simulink interface in FAST.Farm. Figure 4 illustrates the setup of the wind farm used in this case study. In section 3.1, three wind turbines are simulated in both FAST.Farm and the FAST.Farm & MATLAB interface to investigate the communication time between MATLAB and FAST.Farm. In section 3.2, a wind farm is simulated in FAST.Farm and controlled through the MATLAB/Simulink interface in order to validate the working of the interface. An Active Power Controller (APC) is used in this paper as a control example. The APC is based on power tracking controllers [21, 22]. A power tracking controller steers the power generated by wind turbines in order to establish a stable power supply to the grid.

Figure 4: An instantaneous horizontal slice of flow output taken from FAST.Farm.

3.1. Communication Time Experiment

Three 10 MW wind turbines are simulated in both FAST.Farm and the FAST.Farm & MATLAB interface to compare the simulation time, see Table 1. No wind farm controller is implemented in this comparison. Therefore, the difference in simulation time indicates the communication

time between FAST.Farm and MATLAB. Table 1 shows that the interface adds no significant overhead. The simulation time is of the order of real time, depending on the chosen turbine-level time-step. The difference between these two simulations lies in the fact that in the MATLAB interface simulation the avrSWAP matrix is exchanged between MATLAB and FAST.Farm. Values may differ from machine to machine. Such a simulation of three aligned wind turbines in FLORIS would be in the order of seconds on a desktop PC, and in SOWFA in the order of days on a cluster of 10^2 CPU's [23].

Table 1: Simulation time of FAST.Farm and the FAST.Farm & MATLAB interface.

	FAST.Farm	MATLAB interface
Total Real Time	3.06 min	3.24 min
Total CPU Time	28.9 min	29.0 min
Simulation CPU Time	28.8 min	29.0 min
Simulated Time	10.0 min	10.0 min
Time Ratio (Sim/CPU)	0.347	0.345

3.2. Controlled Wind Farm Simulation

A wind plant consisting of three wind turbines is simulated considering the scenario of high wake interaction, see Figure 4. With the implemented APC, the wind plant responds to grid requirements through control of plant power output. First, in section 3.2.1 the wind turbine power tracking controller is briefly explained. Next, in section 3.2.2 the wind farm power tracking controller is clarified. Section 3.2.3 closes this chapter by showing the results of the controllers simulated in FAST.Farm.

3.2.1. Power Tracking Controller at Wind Turbine Level In this section, we will present the implementation at the wind turbine level of the power tracking controller designed by the authors in Silva et al. [24] [9]. The controller receives the current blade pitch angle, generator torque, and rotor speed as input from FAST.Farm. Subsequently, the controller determines the updated blade pitch angle and generator torque in order to match the power output with the reference signal. Two operational modes can be distinguished in the power tracking controller using the input signals from FAST.Farm. The controller either forces the turbine to track the power reference or operates in greedy mode when the power reference exceeds the maximum available power in the wind. In the power tracking mode, a pitch controller regulates the rotor speed to a rotor speed reference while greedy torque control is applied. In the greedy mode, the main objective is to extract the maximum available power from the wind limited by electro-mechanical constraints.

3.2.2. Power Tracking Controller at Wind Farm Level Wind farm power tracking controllers can be used, for example, for thrust balancing, wake-loss compensation, load-limiting, and turbulent wind fluctuation compensation [9, 25]. The wind farm controller tested in this paper uniformly distributes the power references over the number of turbines in the farm to follow a power command signal provided by the system operator. The Automatic Generation Control (AGC) signal is used as the power reference signal [21]. The AGC signal lasts for 1000 seconds

but starts fluctuating after 300 seconds to allow time for the wakes to develop and propagate. Figure 5 shows the block diagram of the wind farm controller in combination with the wind turbine controllers used in this case study. Both, the wind farm and wind turbine controller are designed within MATLAB. See Algorithm 1 for the implementation of this structure in MATLAB.

Figure 5: Block diagram visualizing the controller interface between MATLAB and FAST.Farm.

3.2.3. Results This subsection demonstrates the interaction between the wind turbine & farm controller in MATLAB and FAST.Farm. Figure 6 shows the results of the simulation, these results validate the working of the interface. For this simulation, an inflow wind speed of 10 m/s is used. The first 300 seconds of the simulation are omitted, as some time is needed to start up the turbines and develop and propagate the wakes.

Figure 6: Simulation results of APC simulated in FAST.Farm

4. Conclusion

In this paper the first, to the best of the authors' knowledge, step in creating a full-purpose MATLAB/Simulink interface in FAST.Farm was presented. The capabilities of FAST.Farm for control design purposes has been extended through a co-simulation with MATLAB/Simulink. The case study in this paper shows that MATLAB/Simulink can be used as an add-on to FAST.Farm. Messages, by means of the avrSWAP matrix, can be sent back and forth between MATLAB/Simulink and FAST.Farm. Controllers can be constructed at both wind farm and turbine levels. This interface supports the development and testing of advanced closed-loop control at the wind farm level. In addition, the interface barely affects the simulation time. Future work will focus on further implementing closed-loop controllers at the wind farm level, as in [9, 26]. The interface will be linked to the open wfc platform to extend its capabilities. Moreover, using wind farm models, such as FLORIS in the Simulink-wfc-platform from the FarmConnors project [27] and predictive controllers [28–30] will be explored.

Code availability

The MATLAB/Simulink interface used in this paper can be found at GitHub [31].

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